

THE ROLE OF HISTORICAL SOURCES IN STUDYING THE HISTORY OF GURGANCH CITY

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Annotation: This article presents the importance of historical sources and the analysis of the information contained in them in the study of the past of the city of Gurganch, one of the historical cities of Ancient Khorezm. Also, modern sources for studying the history of Gurganch were analyzed and comments were made about their historical significance.

Key words: Gurganch, scientific works, observations, travels, Sultan Sanjar, Old Urganch, Shajarai Turk, encyclopedia, architectural structures, invasion of Central Asia.

There are no scientific studies rich in extensive information about the city of Gurganch in our modern times. It can be seen that not only Gurganch, but also the Khorezm region, regional accurate chronicles and excellent scientific works on monuments are rare. However, Khorezm is mentioned in Beruni's "Kitobul-Musamara fi Akhbaril-Khorazm" book. Some parts of this work, which have not reached us, have reached today through the works of Bayhaqi, along with some chapters in the sections related to the Ghaznavids. Information about the ancient people of Khorezm, the culture of Khorezm, and the African dynasty can be used in the work of Beruni of Khorezm, called "Osor ul Baqiya".

There are also many authors who visited Gurganch and during their travels, they described their observations in their works. The most prominent of them is Ibn Fadlan. Ibn Fadlan, who was part of the embassy delegation sent by the Abbasid caliph to the Bulgarian ruler, was also in Gurganch during his trip, and in his later works he mentioned information about the city's lifestyle and climate. Another travelogue is the famous work of Ibn Battuta of Tanjar, the greatest traveler of the Middle Ages, known as "Sayohatul Ibn Battuta". During his 28 years of brief travels, Ibn Battuta met the ruler of the city of Gurganch, which was under the rule of the Golden Horde, and provided valuable information about this city. He lives in this city for a while. In his work, he described a lot of information, from the lifestyle of people in Gurganch to housing construction, from religious life to food culture. The Florentine Italian merchant Francesco Baltucci Pegolotti, who prepared his masterpiece on trade routes and trade

goods, visited Gurganj in 1340 and emphasized the commercial importance of the city in his work on trade.

We can also give many examples of modern books, articles and encyclopedias about states and dynasties established in the region. Along with encyclopedia articles on Gurganch and Khorezm region, there are also studies of Turkmenistan, Uzbekistan, and Russia today, but these studies are usually studies of the architectural structures of Khorezm region or Gurganch. The Russians made detailed studies of the region before and after their invasion of Central Asia. However, these studies are usually about the natural resources of the region. Nevertheless, there is some information about the political and cultural history of the city, architectural structures that existed at that time, but have not been preserved, and archaeological excavations. In addition, Russian historians, archaeologists and orientalists conducted exclusive research in Khorezm region and Gurganch. The first of them was the Russian orientalist Alexander Ludvigovich Kuhn (1840-1888). Kuhn conducted research in the region during the period when the Khanate of Khiva joined Russia (1873). After that, the English explorer Henry Lansdell conducted research in the region and photographed the area. From these photos, it is clear that some of the structures that existed at that time have not been preserved. There is information about our topic in his work entitled "Russian Central Asia" dedicated to Central Asia, which is dominated by Russians.

N.I. Veselovsky (1848-1918), who wrote about the geographical region of the Khiva Khanate from the earliest times to the present, gives some information about Gurganch in his work "Essay on History and Geographical Information: From Ancient Times to the Present." Vasilii Vladimirovich Barthold (1869-1930) was a Russian Turkologist and Orientalist, an academician who conducted fundamental and in-depth research on the Turkish history of Central Asia. Many books, in particular, his Turkish translation "Turkistan before the Mongol conquest" (1900) and various encyclopedia articles became the source of our research. In Barthold's "Collection of Works", a total of 511 works, 228 encyclopedia articles were compiled. Alexander Yurievich Yakubovsky (1869-1953), a student of Barthold, was one of the first researchers who went to Gurganch with a scientific committee and studied its architectural structures (1928). Both his work on Gurganch, "Ruins of Urganch", and "On the State of the Golden Horde" became the source of our research. In the 1930s, Nikolay Mikhailovich Bachinsky and prof. Dr. Vladimir Ivanovich Pilyavsky (1910-1984) is an expert on the architectural structure of the region. We especially enjoyed Pilyavsky's book *Kunya-Urganch*⁵¹ from these researchers. Architectural constructions were thoroughly studied, and the work, in which drawings were drawn, served as a source for further research. In this work, Sayan Yuksel also studied the architectural structure of the area using drawings. Sergey Pavlovich Tolstov (1907-1946) is one of the people who conducted fundamental research and archaeological excavations in the Khorezm

region. Tolstov, who conducted archaeological excavations in the region in 1948, 1950 and 1952, wrote a study entitled "Ancient Khorezm" and many articles and works about the Khorezm region. His works contain a lot of information about the most ancient history and ruins of Khorezm. In our research, the work of Nazar Halimov, who is known as an Orientalist and Arab expert, "Journey to Ancient Urganch" is of great value, he researched architectural structures based on rumors about Gurganch. Although the Islamic era of the city was explained or interpreted differently in the studies conducted during the Soviet Union, the author, who knows the Arabic language well, tried to consider the Islamic era in a different dimension. architectural structures were mosques and madrassas, which are a distinctive feature of the Islamic religion.

In addition, Hamra Yusupov, one of today's archeologists and historians, is an expert and historian who studies the architectural structures of Gurganch from a different perspective, and has written many articles and books on this topic. Yusupov, who is currently leading the excavations in the region, generally studies the remains of pre-Islamic architectural structures in Gurganch and tries to link the findings and remains of the Islamic period to the ancient period or Zoroastrianism. Nevertheless, we also enjoyed the space of the work entitled "Khorazm and Gurganch: New Researches" prepared by collecting the old works of Yusupov, who is considered the leading representative of Turkmen historians and archaeologists. The works of Turkish historian Ahmet Zaki Velidi Togan (1890-1970) entitled "Introduction to General Turkish History", "Samples of Khorezm Culture" are among the sources of many modern studies.

The city of Gurganch, whose existence is not known by whom and when it was founded, but whose existence has been mentioned since ancient times, became the capital of Khorezm region when it reached the peak of development. Although it is surrounded by deserts, its location on the edge of the Amudarya has been promoted as an "Oasis in the middle of the desert" due to the canals opened from the river. Khorezm region, where the city is located, hosted many civilizations. Gurganj, which became the center of government with the advent of Islam, was ruled by state governors during the Samanid period. At the end of the Samanid state, the Memunis, who ended the Afrigogul dynasty (385 AD/995 AD), made the city their center and ensured its comprehensive development. During this period, Gurganj, which became a center of science, received scientists from different parts of the Islamic world. The "Academy", where scientific research and scientific discussions are conducted, was also established during this period. Due to the various ethnic and religious groups that settled in the city, the city expanded day by day and became a frequent destination for merchants due to its location on the trade routes. There were no buildings in the whole of Khurasan that could equal the beauty of those built in the central city of Gurganj.

The Memunis, who were in contact with the other powerful states of the region, the Ghaznavids and the Karakhanids, could not prevent Mahmud Ghazni's attempts to conquer the region and in 1017, the dynasty ended. Ghaznavi Mahmud, who appointed himself governor of Gurganch, included this city in the borders of his state. When Seljuks' enemy Shahmelik occupied the city, Seljuks defeated Shahmelik and annexed Gurganch to their lands. The Seljuks contributed to the development of Gurganch with the governors they appointed to the city and carried out construction works. While fighting against the horseless Sultan Sanjar, he also worked to improve the city. During this period, Gurganj succeeded in becoming the capital of the dynasty and the center of science, on a par with Marv, the capital of the Seljuks. Gurganch, the capital of the empire during the time of the Khorezmshahs, dazzled with its beautiful kitchens, palaces, mosques and madrasahs.

The city, where all the riches of the empire were gathered, was surrounded by thick walls, and thanks to the protection provided by large military units, the attacks of Gurlu and Karakhitai on the city were successfully repelled. Gurgench is a very beautiful and prosperous place and hosted many sheikhs and scholars. But as a result of the wrong policy and politics implemented by Alauddin Muhammad, the Mongols attacked the Islamic lands. After a much longer siege than other cities, the Mongols, who captured the city, burned the city, destroyed beautiful buildings and palaces, turned the rose gardens into garbage, destroyed the dam and flooded the city. Thus, the city of prosperity and happiness turned into a ruin where "sheep roam and owls nest," and the city turned into a heap of stones. However, this situation did not last long, and Gurganch, which remained under the control of the Mongols, began to be rebuilt like other cities.

In a very short time, the restored city became a trade center again under the rule of the Golden Horde. Khans of the Golden Horde and governors of Gurganch, who protected scientists, were kind to merchants, helped the development of trade and science, restored the city to its former state. Thus, the city became a populous town with mosques, madrassas, bazaars, hospitals and fine cuisine. This city, where all kinds of trade goods can be easily obtained, where free scientific discussions and debates are held, was attacked again during the reign of the Kunrat-Sufi dynasty. As a result of disagreements between Temur and the governors of Khorezm, Temur made five trips to Khorezm. Temur, who captured Gurganch in his last campaign, was very angry at the uprisings of the Sufi dynasty and the attacks on their lands, so he leveled Gurganch and ordered to plant barley in its place, so that the ruins of the buildings would not become ruins. Although Gurganch was not completely destroyed, three years after its destruction, Timur ordered its reconstruction, but only a part of the city was repaired.

In general, the city of Gurganch occupies an important place in the history of Central Asia with its rich history and beautiful historical buildings. Studying the history of this city from the point of view of different periods will cause us to come across new information. This creates the task of in-depth study of many historical works.

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